

METHODS OF DEVELOPING AESTHETIC TASTE IN FINE ARTS LESSONS

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ANNOTATION

This article examines the development of students' aesthetic taste in fine arts classes from a scientific and pedagogical perspective. The essence of aesthetic taste, its role in personal and spiritual development, and the educational potential of fine arts education are analyzed.

In addition, the article provides practical methodological recommendations for developing aesthetic taste through observation, artistic analysis, creative activity, and the use of national art elements in the educational process.

Keywords: aesthetic taste, fine arts, aesthetic education

In today's globalization and information era, the formation of an individual's aesthetic culture is one of the important tasks of the education system. Aesthetic taste represents a person's ability to perceive, evaluate and consciously respond to existence based on the criteria of beauty. Especially in the younger generation, the development of aesthetic taste is of great importance in their spiritual and moral development.

The formation of aesthetic taste is an important component of the educational process. The discipline of fine arts serves to develop not only the ability to depict, but also the artistic perception of reality, the differentiation of beauty, the understanding of aesthetic values, cultural awareness and artistic thinking. In the current era, the content of the educational process requires the formation of the student's personality as a comprehensive, creative and aesthetically mature person. In this regard, it is relevant to study methods for developing aesthetic taste in fine arts lessons on a scientific basis.

In the current era, the content of the educational process places the need to ensure the comprehensive aesthetic perfection of the individual as an urgent task. The intensification of global cultural processes, the growth of interest in national and world artistic heritage, the expansion of the communicative, educational and spiritual functions of art create the need for a deep integration of aesthetic directions into education. In such conditions, the discipline of fine arts is recognized as an effective didactic tool that serves to form students' worldview, develop artistic perception, understand aesthetic values, and understand the social essence of art.

Aesthetic taste is a complex aesthetic category that refers not only to the student's ability to perceive works of art, but also to the competence to evaluate, understand, and express a personal attitude to them. The formation of aesthetic taste is directly related to psychological, pedagogical, and cultural factors, and the child's age, interest in art, family culture, socio-cultural environment, and the level of artistic experience determine the quality of this process.

The role of fine arts lessons in the development of students' aesthetic culture has long been recognized in pedagogical science. This subject develops in students the skills of perceiving artistic laws between color, form, plasticity, composition, rhythm, objects and images. Through it, students have the opportunity to perceive, evaluate, analyze beauty in nature and society, and master aesthetic values through the creative process. Therefore, the subject of fine arts is a complex educational system that forms not only practical skills, but also aesthetic views.

The relevance of the topic is determined by the increasing functional importance of art in the development of the individual in modern educational concepts. In particular, pedagogical approaches such as integrative education, the STEAM approach, competency-based education, and the promotion of creative thinking interpret the development of aesthetic taste not as an additional quality, but as a

structural component of education. In addition, the expansion of the possibilities of perceiving works of art in the digital environment introduces new methods and tools into the process of aesthetic education.

The purpose of this study is to analyze effective pedagogical methods that develop the aesthetic taste of students in fine arts classes and substantiate their functional significance in the educational process. The tasks of the research include a theoretical interpretation of the concept of aesthetic taste, identification of the aesthetic and educational potential of fine arts, study of methods and pedagogical conditions for the development of aesthetic taste, and assessment of their educational effectiveness.

Fine arts lessons are an important pedagogical tool for developing students' aesthetic thinking, artistic taste and creative abilities. During these lessons, students learn to feel and understand beauty through color, form, composition and images. Education through art is one of the most effective ways to form aesthetic taste.

The development of aesthetic taste in fine arts education is a multi-factorial pedagogical process, which is aimed at forming the student's artistic perception, aesthetic views, emotional sensitivity, figurative thinking and artistic evaluation skills. Effective organization of this process requires the use of various methods. Methods are used in harmony with the age and psychological characteristics of students, aesthetic needs, artistic experience and the content of the lesson.

First of all, the method of visual observation plays an important role in the formation of aesthetic taste. By observing natural landscapes, architectural monuments, sculptures, examples of applied arts, and fine art, students develop the ability to distinguish beauty and perceive color, form, and compositional structure. This method increases students' artistic receptivity and creates the initial foundation for aesthetic appreciation.

The second important direction is the method of emotional-aesthetic analysis, which involves interpreting the artistic idea, color harmony, rhythm of form, light and shadow, image content, and artistic solutions in works of art in an emotional context. In the process of aesthetic analysis, students understand the artistic differences between works, form aesthetic criteria, and begin to acquire artistic evaluation competencies.

The artistic-associative method also expands aesthetic thinking. Through associative thinking, students idealize images in reality and perceive them in a poetic and symbolic form. This method activates the mechanisms of fantasy, imagination, and creative thinking and encourages not only repetition, but also figurative interpretation of art.

One of the most active tools for developing aesthetic taste is the method of creative practice. Creative processes such as drawing, sketching, composing, collage, designing, and modeling help students gain artistic experience. Through practical activities, the student participates in the process of creating beauty and tests aesthetic requirements in his personal experience.

In modern conditions, methods based on digital technologies are also gaining importance. Virtual galleries, electronic museums, 3D modeling programs, multimedia presentations on the history of art expand aesthetic views. Digital platforms form the student's interpretation of color, plasticity, composition and stylistic differences in a modern context.

Also, methods of comparison and artistic evaluation are used in the development of aesthetic taste. By comparing works of art in terms of era, school, style, genre or authorship, a system of aesthetic criteria is formed in students. In the process of artistic evaluation, a personal aesthetic position, critical thinking and artistic taste are strengthened.

The complex use of these methods serves to deepen aesthetic perception in students, expand artistic thinking, increase emotional sensitivity and, most importantly, the conscious formation of

aesthetic taste. As a result, fine arts classes strengthen their position as one of the functional mechanisms for the development of aesthetic culture.

Aesthetic taste is a person's ability to perceive and evaluate works of art, natural landscapes, and beauty in everyday life. Aesthetic taste is inextricably linked with the general cultural level of a person, his aesthetic views, and his spiritual world.

From a pedagogical point of view, the development of aesthetic taste forms in students the skills of understanding beauty, expressing a conscious attitude to works of art, creative thinking, and aesthetic evaluation. This process plays an important role in the harmonious development of a person.

In fine arts lessons, it is important to use various pedagogical methods to develop aesthetic taste. These methods should be used taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students.

The method of observation and analysis is of particular importance in developing students' aesthetic perception. Through this method, students begin to understand the harmony of colors, shapes, composition and artistic solutions in works of art more deeply.

In the process of practical creative activity, students independently express their aesthetic views by drawing and creating compositions. This process serves to develop their creative thinking and artistic taste.

The use of examples of national art forms students' understanding of national aesthetic values and a sense of respect for them. The use of examples of miniature, applied decorative art and folk crafts enriches aesthetic education.

In conclusion, fine arts lessons are an effective pedagogical tool in developing students' aesthetic taste. The systematic and purposeful use of the recommended methods serves to enhance the artistic taste of students and to form them as aesthetically perfect individuals.

The educational process aimed at developing aesthetic taste positively changes students' attitudes not only to art, but also to life.

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